

THE STUDY ON THE ATTITUDE OF THE ORGANIC FARMERS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO THE COIMBATORE DISTRICT

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Abstract:

Agriculture is the backbone of our country, it provides all the necessary food items to all the living creatures by direct or indirect means, also it becomes necessary to concentrate on organic farming to maintain sustainability, openness, independence, health, and safety. The changes in agriculture has taken a quantum jump during Green Revolution such changes have resulted in environmental pollution, degradation of soil health, loss of bio-diversity, ill-effects of the agro chemicals and others. To get rid off from these problems again we are changing our sight towards organic farming.

Key Words: Organic, Agriculture & Farming

Introduction:

Agriculture is the life line of humanity. Any change in agriculture will result in corresponding change in the life of people and of nature and vice versa too. There has been a very rapid change in the way we do farming in the past few decades. It is characterized mainly by the dominance of machinery and chemical technology in agriculture replacing the traditional wisdom, which has altered the society considerably. Everything in nature is balanced. If we disturb the nature it will result in series of changes within and without nature which will ultimately affect the society adversely. Now exactly that is what has happened to Agriculture. Previously agriculture was the part and parcel of nature. Over years agriculture has undergone several changes, thus drifting away from nature.

Organic Farming

It is a form of agriculture that relies on techniques such as crop rotation, green manure, compost, and biological pest control. Organic farming uses fertilizers if they are considered natural (such as bone meal from animals or pyrethrin from flowers), but it excludes or strictly limits the use of various methods including synthetic petrochemical fertilizers and pesticides; plant growth regulators such as hormones; antibiotic use in livestock; genetically modified organisms; human sewage sludge; and nanomaterial's. For reasons including sustainability, openness, independence, health, and safety.

Statement of the Problem:

In India, the farmers have followed the path for organic food production, but the share of India in the world organic market is less than one percent. The main problem of the study is to know about the attitude of the farmers towards organic farming.

Review of Literature:

D. James Mohan (2014) in his study analysed the attitude of farmers towards the cultivation of organic vegetables who are now engaged in organic and conventional vegetable cultivation. Majority of the organic farmers (86.67%) had a favourable attitude towards organic farming practices followed by more favourable (10%) and less favourable (3.33%) attitude. More than 80 per cent of the conventional farmers had favourable attitude towards organic farming practices. Above 90 per cent of the organic as well as conventional farmers believed that use of organic farming practices was essential for better quality of vegetables. Nearly cent per cent of the conventional farmers reduced the chemical application over the years and increased the application of organic manures.

Kotresha, S. S (2014) in his study investigated the knowledge, and attitude of vegetable growers towards organic farming. A survey method through face-to-face interview by using structured schedule was used to collect data from a total of 30 vegetable growers in Maddur taluk of Mandya district which was selected by using simple random sampling method. The findings of the study show that the knowledge of the respondents on organic farming especially pertaining to the use chemical insecticides, herbicides and fertilizers is need to be improved, their attitude is also still negative, and they are dependent on conventional practices (i.e. chemical) especially to control pests and diseases.

Dr. Suresh Patina (2015) in his study evaluated farmers perception of organic farming and issues associated with it. The study was conducted in Madhya Pradesh, India. The state of Madhya Pradesh consists of 39 districts; out of these a convenient and purposive sampling technique was used to select 100 respondents from 50 villages of Khargone district of Nimar region. Descriptive statistics and factor analysis were used to

present the findings of the study while the Chi-square analysis was used to test the study hypotheses. Study revealed that 67% of respondents have positive perception towards organic farming. A revealed a positive perception of organic farming with significant relationships between age, educational background, farm size, benefits of organic farming, and social factors. This indicates that the communities will have high adoption rate of innovations related to organic farming and other agricultural policies.

Objective of the Study:

- ✓ To study the attitude of the organic producers towards various strategies followed in organic farming, Consumers, Certifications and initiatives provided by the government.
- ✓ To study the relationship between the socio-economic factors and the attitude of the organic farmers.

Scope of the Study:

The main objective of the study is to know the attitude of the organic farm producers in marketing their produce. This study will be useful for the researcher for future prospects. This research helps in understanding the present scenario faced by the organic product cultivators.

Limitation of the Study:

- ✓ The study depends upon primary data and the data is valued based on the response by the respondents.
- ✓ The sample size is limited to 50 due to time constraints
- ✓ The area of the study limited to Coimbatore district only.

Research Methodology:

Area of the Study:

The research study was done only in Coimbatore District.

Research Design:

Research design is the detailed plan of conducting a research study. Descriptive research design has been used in the study. Descriptive analysis attempts to explain systematically a trend, and provides data concerning attitudes and preferences towards a problem.

Nature and Source of Data:

The study is based on Interview Schedule method and the data has been collected from various farmers in Coimbatore.

Sample Size: 50 farmers

Statistical Tools Used For the Study:

- The statistical tools have been used to analyse the primary data.
- ✓ Simple percentage analysis,
- ✓ Weighted average method and
- ✓ t-test

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Personal Information (Age)

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
Up to 35 yrs.	4	8
36-45 yrs.	19	38
46-55 yrs.	12	24
56-65 yrs.	11	22
Above 65 yrs.	4	8
Total	50	100.0

Interpretation:

It is seen from the above table that 38% of the respondents belong to the age group of 36- 45yrs and 24% of the respondents belong to the age group of 46-55yrs, 22% of the respondents belong to the age group of 56-65yrs. The Majority of the respondents i.e., 62% belong to the age group of 36- 55yrs.

Table 2: Gender

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
Male	47	94
Female	3	6
Total	50	100.0

Interpretation:

It is seen from the above table that is 94% of the respondents are Male and 6% of the respondents are Female. The Majority of the respondents involved in the organic farming are male.

Table 3: Educational Qualification

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
No Formal Education	2	4
School Education	35	70

Under Graduation	9	18
Post-Graduation	3	6
Profession	1	2
Total	50	100.0

Interpretation:

It is seen from the above table that 70% of the respondents comes under School Education and 18% of the respondents have completed their Under Graduation. So, Majority of the respondents i.e., 70% of the respondents comes under School Education.

Table 4: Annual Income

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
Below Rs.1 lakh	2	4
Rs.1 - 2 lakhs	15	30
Rs.2 - 3 lakhs	21	42
Rs.3 - 4 lakhs	8	16
Rs.4 - 5 lakhs	3	6
Above Rs.5 Lakhs	1	2
Total	50	100.0

Interpretation:

It is seen from the above table that 42% of the respondents are earning Rs.2-3 lakhs as their annual income from organic farming followed by 30% of the respondents earning Rs.1-2 lakhs as their annual income. The Majority of the respondents i.e., 72% belong to the income group of Rs. 1-3 lakhs.

Attitude towards Organic Farming:

The respondents were asked to state their Attitude on a set of factors constructed to measure the attitude. The scale consisted of 5 point rating scale. The rating was assigned as Highly Agree 5, Agree 4, Moderately Agree 3, Disagree 2, and Strongly Disagree 1. Mean ratings were found out for each item and are given in the following table.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics

Particulars	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	S.D
Nutritional values of organic products are higher than the conventional products.	50	1.00	5.00	3.7354	.89283
OF is more complicated than chemical farming	50	1.00	5.00	3.6718	1.03591
OF requires prior soil treatment	50	1.00	5.00	3.6387	.99321
Water resources have to be clean and without any pollutants if OF should be adopted	50	1.00	5.00	3.4224	.92841
Only good quality seeds of known source can be used in organic farming	50	1.00	5.00	3.8117	.86612
OF requires adding organic fertilizer	50	1.00	5.00	3.5802	1.01233
Organic agriculture reduces the risks of environmental pollution	50	1.00	5.00	3.4249	1.00259
It is essential to provide the soil with organic fertilizers in organic farming	50	1.00	5.00	3.5776	.91178
Organic farming does not need synthetic pesticide application	50	1.00	5.00	3.5954	.92122
Organic farming is the application of innovations compatible to the local issues	50	1.00	5.00	3.4682	.93385
Organic farming will only troublesome the farmers because it needs more attention	50	1.00	5.00	3.4656	1.03975
Organic farming is very difficult to implement due to difficulties in obtaining organic materials	50	1.00	5.00	3.5954	1.00340
Agricultural crops in organic agriculture are grown by using crop residues, green manures etc.	50	1.00	5.00	3.4962	1.04765
Organic products contain very small amounts of chemicals and little or no pesticide residues	50	1.00	5.00	3.5573	.90486
Best organic products are realized from the crops grown on low levels of nitrates	50	1.00	5.00	3.6005	.91791
Demonstration and training programmes must be implemented on the organic farming methods.	50	1.00	5.00	3.4071	.87607

Do you agree that many fungal infections and nematodes can be controlled without using the pesticides?	50	1.00	5.00	3.5344	.88321
Can insect-pests and crops diseases be controlled without using pesticides with bio resistance methods?	50	1.00	5.00	3.7455	.88432
Organic farming is a way to preserve old traditions and traditional values.	50	1.00	5.00	3.7303	.90550
Future of organic farming lies in consumers hands.	50	1.00	5.00	3.5318	.94201
OF will conserve water resources compared to ordinary farming	50	1.00	5.00	3.3995	.98234
OF does not generate poisonous fumes in the air	50	1.00	5.00	3.6361	.89637
Organic fertiliser used in farm does not affect one's health	50	1.00	5.00	3.7583	.89505
NOF will destroy soil, water and natural resources surrounding farm	50	1.00	5.00	3.7405	.94966
Consumers tend to buy more organic agricultural products	50	1.00	5.00	3.5674	.91259
Consumers can buy organic agricultural products readily from the farm	50	1.00	5.00	3.4682	.95812
Organic products marketing gain more support from the government	50	1.00	5.00	3.3588	.96417
Organic product is cheaper than ordinary product	50	1.00	5.00	3.4198	.94724
Organic farming will only be benefiting the consumers not the producers	50	1.00	5.00	3.4224	.95282
Total OF cost is higher than chemical farming cost	50	1.00	5.00	3.2850	1.05473
OF can give more profit than products from chemical farming	50	1.00	5.00	3.4377	1.10970
OF can translate into decreased expenditure by using own organic fertiliser and own family labour	50	1.00	5.00	3.1527	.99340
OF and NOF products are the same prices	50	1.00	5.00	3.0814	1.00432
Organic farming will decrease the production cost by reducing the input purchases	50	1.00	5.00	3.5725	.97440
Organic farming can increase the income of farmers	50	1.00	5.00	3.5369	.91712
Despite the higher prices for organic products, the citizen will still prefer to buy organic ones	50	1.00	5.00	3.4860	.92053

Interpretation:

It is seen from the above table that for the most of the items the attitude of the respondents varies between a minimum of 1 to maximum of 5. The highest mean rating is 3.8 for Only good quality seeds of known source can be used in organic farming, that is the attitude level for this item falls between Moderately agree and Agree. Most of the items have mean ratings above 3.5 and below 4 (i.e.) the attitude of the respondents to most of the items falls near Agree.

The attitude score were calculated to measure the overall attitude of the farmer regarding Organic Farming. The ratings given for the items in the attitude scale were added for each respondent to get the attitude score. Higher the score more will be the attitude level .The attitude scores were compared among the groups of several personal and farming practices variables. The following table gives the mean attitude scores for the groups of selected personal and farming practices variables.

Table 6: Attitude of the Respondent and Personal information

Particulars		Awareness Score on OF			F Value/T Value	Table Value	Sig
		Mean	S.D	No.			
Age	Up to 35 yrs.	67.93	7.47	4	2.176		Ns
	36-45 yrs.	69.29	12.56	19			
	46-55 yrs.	72.19	10.12	12			
	56-65 yrs.	70.34	12.23	11			
	Above 65 yrs.	74.39	11.31	4			
Total		70.53	11.58	50			
Gender	Male	70.66	11.33	47	0.781		Ns
	Female	68.85	14.73	3			
Total		70.53	11.58	50			

Educational Qualification	No Formal Education	71.16	11.62	2	0.631	Ns
	School Education	69.96	11.72	35		
	Under Graduation	71.79	10.13	9		
	Post-Graduation	72.46	10.44	3		
	Profession	73.18	17.97	1		
Total		70.53	11.58	50		
Annual Income	BelowRs.1 lakh	62.29	4.76	2	5.030	**
	Rs.1 - 2 lakhs	67.37	11.61	15		
	Rs.2 - 3 lakhs	71.96	10.19	21		
	Rs.3 - 4 lakhs	73.73	11.67	8		
	Rs.4 - 5 lakhs	71.57	18.01	3		
	Above Rs.5 Lakhs	72.67	10.82	1		
Total		70.53	11.58	50		

Interpretation:

Attitude Score by Age:

The mean attitude scores found for different age groups showed that the respondents in the age group of above 65 years have highest means score of 74.39. The lowest awareness level with a mean score of 67.93 was found for below 35 years of age group.

Attitude Score by Gender:

The mean attitude scores found for the gender showed that the male respondents have highest means score of 70.66. The female respondents show lowest attitude level with a mean score of 68.85.

Attitude Score by Educational Qualification:

The mean attitude scores found for Educational Qualification showed that the respondents completed professional degree have highest means score of 73.18. The respondents with the School education have lowest attitude level with a mean score of 69.96.

Attitude Score by Annual Income:

The mean attitude scores found for different Income level showed that the respondents in the income level of 3-4 lakhs have highest means score of 73.73. The lowest attitude level with a mean score of 62.29 was found for below 1 lakh of income level.

Interpretation for T- Test Tables:

In order to find whether the attitude scores differs significantly according to the groups of selected personal variable the following research Hypothesis was framed and tested.

Hypothesis:

The attitude scores do not differ significantly among the groups of age, gender, education and income.

Result:

t-test were conducted to test the above hypothesis. The test results show that the calculated f/t values are less than the table values for Age, Gender, Educational Qualification where as the calculated value is more than the table value for income. Hence the hypothesis is rejected with respect to Income only. For Age, Gender, Educational Qualification the hypothesis was accepted. Hence it is inferred that the attitude of the respondents differs significantly among Income groups and the attitude level is higher for income group of 3-4 lakh and lower for the less than 1 lakh income group.

Findings of the Study:

- ✓ The Majority of the respondents i.e., 62% belong to the age group of 36- 55yrs.
- ✓ The Majority of the respondents (i.e., 94%) involved in the organic farming are male.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents i.e., 70% of the respondents comes under School Education.
- ✓ The Majority of the respondents i.e., 72% belong to the income group of Rs. 1-3 lakhs.
- ✓ The highest mean rating is 3.8 for Only good quality seeds of known source can be used in organic farming, that is the attitude level for this item falls between Moderately agree and Agree. Most of the items have mean ratings above 3.5 and below 4 (i.e.) the attitude of the respondents to most of the items falls near Agree.
- ✓ The mean attitude scores found for different age groups showed that the respondents in the age group of above 65 years have highest means score of 74.39.
- ✓ The mean attitude scores found for the gender showed that the male respondents have highest means score of 70.66.
- ✓ The mean attitude scores found for Educational Qualification showed that the respondents completed professional degree have highest means score of 73.18.
- ✓ The mean attitude scores found for different Income level showed that the respondents in the income level of 3-4 lakhs have highest means score of 73.73.

Suggestions:

- ✓ The government can show much more interest toward organic farming. The organic farmers may provide with subsidies, awards and rewards for practicing organic farming successfully.
- ✓ More number of training programmes can be conducted for the farmers for adopting new methodologies and techniques in organic farming.
- ✓ Direct sale method like Ulavarsandhai can be separately adopted for organic farm products.
- ✓ Certification process and cost can be diluted in order to encourage more number of farmers to obtain Organic farming certificates.

Conclusion:

The organic food industry in the world with a good growth rate with most of the thing concentrated. To supplement this demand, farmers have taken to organic farming for getting price premiums. In India, the farmers have followed the path for organic food production, but the share of India in the world, organic market is very less. Even though large number of farmers and farm labours are migrating from this sector. This reveals clearly that there is no chance to have growth in income of farmers and farm labours in the existing farming practice called conventional farming may be used. This study reveals that now most of the farmers doing organic farming are satisfied with this farming practice.

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